

Supplemental Data For: Endotracheal Tube Mucus as a Source of Airway Mucus for Rheological Study

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Supplemental Methods

S1.1 Endotracheal Tube Collection

Endotracheal tubes (ETTs) from patients were collected post-operation from the Department of Surgery at the University of North Carolina (UNC) Hospital. Collection was approved under UNC IRB #11-0413. Upon removal of the ETT following surgery, the tip of each ETT was excised and mucus was collected from the tips by low-speed centrifugation. Samples found to contain visible blood were discarded. All retained samples are summarized in terms of demographics and basic composition in Table S1. The three samples that were selected for glycomics analysis at the University of Georgia in the lab of MT are indicated by secretor status in the age column of Table S1. Comparison of the entire sample set to the isotonic set of interest in the main text is given in Figure 1 and its related descriptions.

S1.2 Proteomics of ETT Mucus

An aliquot of 100 μ l of pooled ETT mucus was prepared for analysis with the FASP (Filter Aided Sample Preparation) method. Briefly, samples were denatured with 800 μ l of 6M GuHCl (pH 8.0) and reduced by adding DTT to a final concentration of 20 mM for 1 hour at 65 degree. After reduction, samples were alkylated with iodoacetamide (Sigma) at a final concentration of 50 mM for 1 h at 25°C in the dark. Samples were centrifuged at 14,000 x g for 10 min, and the filter was washed twice with 50 mM ammonium hydrogen carbonate (NH_4HCO_3). 0.5 μ g modified trypsin (proteomics grade, Sigma) was added and samples were incubated 18 h at 37°C. The peptides solutions were concentrated by vacuum centrifuge system. Peptides were dissolved in 30 μ L 0.1 % formic acid water. Mass spectrometry experiments was performed with a Dionex ultimate 3000 RSLCnano system coupled to a hybrid quadrupole orbitrap mass spectrometer with a Nano spray source (Q-Exactive, Thermo Fisher, Bremen, Germany). Samples (3 μ L) were loaded into a trap column (Acclaim PepMap 100, 100 μ m x 2 cm, nanoViper C18 5 μ m 100 Å),

at 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ with aqueous solution containing 0.1 % (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid and 2 % acetonitrile. The column used for peptides separation is an Acclaim PepMap RSLC, 75 μm x 15 cm, nanoViper C18 2 μm 100 \AA . LC – MS run is 120 minutes long, with two liquid phases: 97% water 3% Acetonitrile 0.1% Formic Acid (buffer A) and Acetonitrile 0.1% Formic Acid (buffer B).

The gradient of the run (120 minutes) is reported in Table S2. Data were acquired at a resolution of 70,000 at m/z 200, target AGC value of $5e5$, maximum fill times of 200 ms, a multiplex degree of 6 with an isolation width of 3 m/z . Proteins were identified by searching against most current human database (Proteome Discover 1.4) and quantified using Scaffold, Version 4 (Proteome Software Inc.), using the normalized total precursor intensity.

S1.3 Immunohistochemical Staining of ETT Mucus

MUC5B and MUC5AC immunohistochemical staining for flake density and composition. BALF (20 μl) was applied to glass microscopy slides using a cytocentrifuge (StatSpin CytoFuge 2, Beckman Coulter, Inc.). Slides were fixed with neutral buffered formalin (10 vol%), washed with Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS), and blocked with bovine serum albumin (3 wt% in DPBS) for 1 h at room temperature. MUC5AC and MUC5B were immunohistochemically stained (0.4 and 0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ with mouse anti-MUC5AC and rabbit anti-MUC5B antibodies, respectively) as well as fibrin and PRR4 (0.1mg.mL mouse anti-fibrin and rabbit anti-PRR4 diluted 1:1,000, respectively), slides washed with DPBS three times (10 min), exposed to secondary antibodies (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Alexa 488 and 594 anti-rabbit and mouse, respectively) and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 1 h at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then washed with DPBS (10 min) and mounted with Fluorsave (Calbiochem). Quantitative measurements of stain intensity from confocal images were obtained with an Olympus FV 1000 (Olympus, Hamilton, Bermuda).

Supplemental Results

S2.1 Immunohistochemical Imaging of ETT Mucus Components

Mucins are the primary gel-forming component of mucus in healthy airways, though other components including DNA may also be present. Accordingly, we stained a single sample of ETT mucus for DNA, MUC5AC, and MUC5B (Figure S1). Most DNA in ETT mucus appears to be located in cells with polymorphonuclear neutrophils, ciliated epithelial cells, and macrophages visible in the samples (Figure S1A, B). MUC5AC was present (Figure S1C, D), but appeared to be less abundant than MUC5B (Figure S1E, F), which appeared throughout the sample. The merged view of all imaging channels (Figure S1G, H) did not reveal a general pattern of colocalization between the mucins or DNA.

Proteomics data in Table 3 of the main text identified proteins secreted by the submucosal glands and the airway surface epithelium in ETT mucus in addition to proteins (i.e. serum albumin and serotransferrin) associated with serum leak. A second aliquot of ETT mucus was stained again for DNA (Figure S2A), and also fibrin (Figure S2B) and PRR4 (Figure S2C). DNA was mostly intranuclear as above in Figure S1A and S1B. Relatively diffuse fibrin staining was detected (Figure S2B). PRR4 was present throughout most of the sample image (Figure S2C), which

confirmed the mass spectrometry findings (Table 3, main text) that a portion of the ETT mucus originated from the submucosal gland.

S2.2 Comparison of CF Sputum Power-law Scaling to ETT and HBE Stock Mucus Solutions

Spontaneously obtained CF sputum often registers % solids measurements in excess of those investigated in the ETT stock solutions of the main text. However, as shown in Figure S3, CF sputum η^* obtained via cone-and-plate rheometry follows a similar power law rheology to both ETT and HBE mucus sample types (i.e. $\eta^* \sim c^{4.8}$ in sputum). Figure S3 presents the data from Figure 7A with η^* values from n=8 spontaneous sputum samples from patients with CF. The power-law curve of best fit to the CF sputum data is shown as a dashed line, extrapolated to lower values of % solids to guide the eye. While these sputa represent mucus from individual patients and not pooled volumes, the strong agreement lends credence to our claim that ETT mucus can be an analog of diseased mucus for study.

S2.3 Frequency Dependence in Microrheology of ETT and HBE Mucus

Hill and colleagues have previously shown that HBE mucus illustrates a frequency-dependent rheology in addition to concentration dependence¹. Figure S4 reproduces those findings as a comparator for the frequency-dependence of concentration-tuned ETT mucus rheology. Figure S4 (left panel) illustrates that G' of ETT mucus monotonically increases with increasing frequency in a manner comparable to that of HBE mucus. Figure S4 (right panel) illustrates a similar monotonic relationship for G'' of ETT mucus but with improved concordance with HBE mucus. Sol-gel transition appears to occur for ETT mucus at roughly 4% solids at frequencies 1 Hz and above as evidenced by $G' > G''$ under those conditions. The 0.1 Hz measurement indicates that ETT mucus behaves as a gel across physiological concentrations under low frequency strains applied by the microscopic probes enmeshed within the gel.

Table S1 Patient data for all ETT samples obtained.

Age	Sex	Race	Intubation Time (hours)	Anesthesia Info	Sample Volume (μl)	% solids	Na+ (mM)	K+ (mM)	Na/K ratio	Fold Conc.	Fold Conc. w/ K
67	F	Black	6	isoflurane	200	4.69	284.44	63.28	4.49	2.37	2.45
38	F	Asian	1	isoflurane	250	4.42	178.17	67.66	2.63	1.48	2.10
59	F	Cauc	4	sevoflurane	200	9.50	191.57	73.16	2.62	1.60	2.26
63	M	Cauc	3.5	sevoflurane	550	3.14	148.76	46.62	3.19	1.24	1.55
70	M	Cauc	7	isoflurane	400	4.48	138.92	23.72	5.86	1.16	1.05
60	M	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	350	7.37	127.65	56.88	2.24	1.06	1.67
66	M	Cauc	1.5	isoflurane	400	12.57	227.87	69.46	3.28	1.90	2.34
49	M	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	550	12.16	316.66	84.93	3.73	2.64	3.02
30 +/-	M	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	700	7.36	235.07	94.50	2.49	1.96	2.87
26	M	Cauc	1.3	IVA	250	8.30	482.50	73.47	6.57	4.02	3.48
39 +/-	F	Hisp	3	sevoflurane	450	6.14	828.91	71.74	11.55	6.91	4.89
61	F	Cauc	4.5	isoflurane	550	6.18	297.03	101.44	2.93	2.48	3.27
72	F	Cauc		sevoflurane	180	12.83	194.80	58.43	3.33	1.62	1.98
51	F	Black	2	sevoflurane	700	7.16	186.02	93.75	1.98	1.55	2.65
49	F	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	200	2.03	195.24	81.51	2.40	1.63	2.44
30	F	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	250	12.73	286.56	55.44	5.17	2.39	2.30
83	M	Cauc	1.75	isoflurane	450	12.70	173.29	52.55	3.30	1.44	1.77
24	F	Black	2.5	sevoflurane	750	6.26	174.06	152.68	1.14	1.45	3.78
68	F	Cauc	3.5	sevoflurane	200	6.36	228.24	71.03	3.21	1.90	2.37
53	F	Black	3.5	isoflurane	550	3.92	296.58	60.60	4.89	2.47	2.45
57	M	Cauc	1.2	sevoflurane	800	2.61	205.09	85.62	2.40	1.71	2.57
54	F	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	350	6.56	222.21	138.90	1.60	1.85	3.70
41	F	Black	2	isoflurane	200	4.36	147.63	62.12	2.38	1.23	1.86
48	M	Cauc	3.5	isoflurane & sevoflurane	450	4.80	323.04	71.30	4.53	2.69	2.77
34 +/+	F	Black	2.5	isoflurane	750	8.29	323.04	71.30	4.53	2.69	2.77
52	F	Cauc	3.5	isoflurane	250	2.78	235.10	79.47	2.96	1.96	2.57
81	M	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	200	6.82	202.45	146.36	1.38	1.69	3.77
38	M	Black	2	sevoflurane	600	2.48	340.35	77.75	4.38	2.84	2.97
38	F	Hisp	1.25	desflurane	500	5.40	768.02	180.27	4.26	6.40	6.81
78	F	Cauc	2.25	isoflurane	550	3.33	238.74	54.30	4.40	1.99	2.08
58	M	Black	2	sevoflurane & IVA+	300	5.35	343.00	76.78	4.47	2.86	2.96
32	F	Black	2	sevoflurane	1050	2.81	408.72	65.38	6.25	3.41	3.01
73	F	Cauc	1	sevoflurane	550	1.95	301.79	60.31	5.00	2.51	2.46
41	F	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	650	2.59	148.47	30.64	4.85	1.24	1.23
51	M	Cauc	2	isoflurane	800	2.14	117.32	31.71	3.70	0.98	1.12
40	M	Black	5	isoflurane	700	4.84	121.08	30.98	3.91	1.01	1.12
67	F	Black	1.5	sevoflurane	1000	5.62	131.80	28.16	4.68	1.10	1.11
61	F	Cauc	1.5	isoflurane	450	3.14	148.47	25.29	5.87	1.24	1.12
35	F	Indian	1.5	sevoflurane	550	10.04	110.52	23.40	4.72	0.92	0.93

45	F	Cauc	1	desflurane	750	1.22	124.92	26.10	4.79	1.04	1.04
58	N	Cauc	3	isoflurane	550	3.45	123.39	47.19	2.61	1.03	1.46
72	M	Cauc	1	sevoflurane	600	3.36	84.39	37.11	2.27	0.70	1.09
84	M	Cauc	1.5	sevoflurane	750	10.43	140.38	45.07	3.11	1.17	1.49
43	F	?	1	isoflurane	950	4.74	161.71	30.02	5.39	1.35	1.27
58	F	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	600	3.39	117.67	29.37	4.01	0.98	1.08
70	F	Cauc	3	isoflurane	650	5.45	120.53	27.07	4.45	1.00	1.04
70	M	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	750	9.39	162.65	23.77	6.84	1.36	1.15
67	M	Indian	6	desflurane	450		143.53	21.09	6.81	1.20	1.02
64	F	Cauc	2.5	TIVA	650	6.34	138.04	28.19	4.90	1.15	1.14
39	M	Cauc	3.5	sevoflurane	600	5.00	117.70	36.70	3.21	0.98	1.22
62	F	Cauc	3	isoflurane	600	8.55	153.06	33.13	4.62	1.28	1.30
34	M	Cauc	2.5	desflurane	650	5.85	166.51	48.19	3.46	1.39	1.66
84	M	Cauc	1.5	isoflurane	1150	3.66	135.55	26.60	5.10	1.13	1.10
68	M	Cauc	1	sevoflurane	600	3.18	125.54	21.07	5.96	1.05	0.94
78	M	Cauc	2.25	isoflurane	650	5.99	221.27	55.30	4.00	1.84	2.03
21	M	Black	1.5	sevoflurane	550	6.26	121.86	45.90	2.65	1.02	1.43
40	F	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	550	4.42	118.82	27.59	4.31	0.99	1.05
67	M	Cauc	4	sevoflurane	500	9.56	154.51	42.29	3.65	1.29	1.49
47	M	Black	2	TIVA	650	3.34	156.46	30.75	5.09	1.30	1.27
47	M	Cauc	2	isoflurane	600	3.00	124.50	30.10	4.14	1.04	1.12
38	M	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane	650	5.97	137.30	29.23	4.70	1.14	1.16
56	F	Cauc	4	isoflurane	450	5.43	68.22	41.07	1.66	0.57	1.11
66	F	Cauc	3	sevoflurane	500	5.54	252.31	59.18	4.26	2.10	2.23
80	M	Cauc	4	sevoflurane	650	3.70	100.46	61.72	1.63	0.84	1.65
43	F	Cauc	2	sevoflurane	700	6.80	95.25	37.03	2.57	0.79	1.14
40	F	Black	1.5	sevoflurane	1150	6.20	189.93	23.64	8.03	1.58	1.26
37	F	Cauc	2	isoflurane	500	7.63	100.16	29.41	3.41	0.83	1.01
68	M	Black	1	isoflurane	1050	2.81	127.49	23.49	5.43	1.06	1.00
51	F	Cauc	2.5	sevoflurane + IVA+INH	550	4.02	106.63	17.96	5.94	0.89	0.80
40	M	Black	2	desflurane	700	3.69	175.18	36.58	4.79	1.46	1.46
43	M	Black	2	sevoflurane	750	3.15	132.49	32.95	4.02	1.10	1.21
20	M	Cauc	3.5	sevoflurane	850	4.25	151.52	39.15	3.87	1.26	1.41
58	M	Black	2.5	sevoflurane	950	4.96	119.84	38.81	3.09	1.00	1.28
87	F	Cauc	3`	sevoflurane	600	3.98	119.96	25.18	4.76	1.00	1.00
63	M	Cauc	3hr	isoflurane	650	3.65	111.96	21.52	5.20	0.93	0.90
48	F	Cauc	4hr	sevoflurane	500		148.75	18.85	7.89	1.24	1.00
43	F	Black	1hr	desflurane	900	5.24	156.53	29.69	5.27	1.30	1.25
Averages	-	-	2.5		581	5.60	197.87	52.87	4.17	1.65	1.88

Table S2 Gradient portions of the ETT mucus pool.

<i>minutes</i>	<i>%B</i>
0-7	4
7-90	30
90-105	80
105-120	4

Figure S1 Immunistochemical imaging of ETT mucus. DNA staining (A,B) indicated that most DNA was intranuclear with little free DNA detected. (B) Polymorphonuclear neutrophils (arrows, black line) and cilia (arrows, white line) are clearly visible. MUC5AC (C,D) is somewhat diffuse relative to MUC5B (E,F), which pervades the sample. No general patterns of colocalization are clearly visible in the channel-merged images (G,H).

Figure S2 Immunistochemical imaging of ETT mucus to elucidate sample origin. DNA staining (A) again indicated that most DNA was intranuclear with little free DNA detected. (B) Fibrin staining was very diffuse, indicating a lack of major epithelial laceration. (C) PRR4 was present throughout most of the sample, confirming mass spectrometry results in Table 3 (main text) that suggested portion of ETT mucus originates in the submucosal gland. No general patterns of co-localization are clearly visible in the channel-merged images (D).

Figure S3 Concentration dependence data from Figure 7A in the main text are shown with η^* vs. % solids in sputum from individual patients with CF added. CF sputa show nearly identical scaling ($\sim c^{4.8}$) as ETT and HBE mucus. Dash line is the power-law curve of best fit to the CF Sputum data ($r=0.72$, $p=0.045$, Spearman test fit to \log_{10} -transformed data).

Figure S4 G' (left) and G'' (right) for ETT and HBE mucus vs. concentration at different frequencies. Both moduli increase monotonically with frequency regardless of sample source. Agreement is generally good between ETT and HBE at each concentration and frequency particularly in G'' .

References

1. Hill, D. B. *et al.* A biophysical basis for mucus solids concentration as a candidate biomarker for airways disease. *PLoS One* **9**, 1–11 (2014).